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EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF STUDENTS BELONGING TO SC/ST COMMUNITIES

Social Work

Dr. K. Arockia Raj

Asst. Professor

PG & Research Dept. of Social Work

Sacred Heart College (Autonomous),

Tirupattur, Vlr Dist – 635 601

Abstract

The Indian tradition has categorized the human beings on various categories. SC/ST people are most vulnerable and neglected for many years from good education and standard of life in India societies. Emotional intelligence has become one of the most important traits needed for any successful person. Hence, a study was carried out in 2011 with 124 SC/ST student respondents to assess their EI status. Factors such as; gender, domicile, academic achievements and socio-economic status have been used to measure the difference in the EI of the SC/ST students of a minority institution. This study revealed that the emotional intelligence is moderate and below among these SC/ST students. The EI significantly differs by gender, domicile and academic achievement of the students. There is positive correlation found between EI and Academic Achievement and not with Socio-economic status. This study has highlighted the importance of Emotional Intelligence education for the SC/ST students.

KEY WORDS: *Emotional Intelligence (EI), Academic Achievement and SC/ST students*

Introduction

Students are challenged with their skills and traits and it is ought to compete in most competitive world to prove ones' abilities. It is most challenging for deprived community

students, specifically the students belonging to SC/ST communities. The education of today focuses much on the cognitive aspect and seldom gives importance to the affective one. It has been accepted by all that education should help the individual to solve the challenges of life and make successful adjustment. This paper presents about the status of Emotional intelligence among the students belonging to SC/ST Communities who were studying in one of the pioneer minority colleges in Tamilnadu.

Literature Review

There are ample literatures are available on the different aspects of Emotional Intelligence and Academic achievement of students. This paper highlights only some of them.

According to Goleman (1995), IQ alone is no more the measure of success. It only accounts to 20% and the rest goes to emotional and social intelligence and luck. Emotional intelligence is comprised of emotional reasoning about our feelings and emotions. It can help to channelize the feelings in constructive direction because feelings affect motivation, learning, memory, attention, concentration, oral expression, written expression and academic success (Kusche & Greenberg 1994).

Belanger (2005) studied the emotional intelligence of undergraduate's students in United States. The researchers found that although student's emotional intelligence was not directly linked to academic success, students with higher levels of emotional intelligence had more self-efficacy and that in turn enhanced their academic performance.

Students who attain high levels of achievement in their academic and career are self-directed learners who have mastered in their cognitive and emotional traits. The cognitive curriculum is overt and focuses on academic content areas, grade point averages, and semester hours. The emotional curriculum is covert and is based on relationships, social activities, recreation, collegiate sports and organizations, as well as, what students want to do at any particular time. The emotional curriculum is skills oriented with behaviours that occur both inside and outside the classroom. These skills, attitudes, and behaviours are important factors associated with student achievement along with success. High levels of emotional intelligence will positively impact personal, academic, and career success (Nelson & Low: 2003).

Specific Objectives

1. To study the status of Emotional Intelligence of SC/ST students in minority institution
2. To examine the association between the emotional intelligence and academic achievements of the SC/ST students
3. To find out whether emotional intelligence and academic achievements differ by the gender and domicile of the SC/ST students
4. To find out whether the emotional intelligence and academic achievement differ by the socio-economic status of the SC/ST students

Hypotheses

1. Academic achievement does not correlate with the emotional intelligence of the SC/ST students
2. The emotional intelligence and academic achievements does not differ by the gender and domicile of the SC/ST students
3. The emotional intelligence and academic achievement does not differ by the socio-economic status of the SC/ST students

Methodology

This study was carried out in the year 2011 at Sacred Heart College, which is one of the pioneering Autonomous colleges in Tamilnadu. It has served many students belonging to marginalized communities. This college is a minority college. This study was done using descriptive design. Stratified disproportionate random sampling was used to select 124 second and third year UG students. Questionnaire was used to measure the emotional intelligence of the students. (Petrides & Furnham: 2006) Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire – Short Form (TEIQue-SF) consists of 30 items designed to measure global trait emotional intelligence, which covers 15 distinct facets was used to measure the emotional intelligence of the students.

Analysis and Interpretation

Core findings in the form of tables have been given below related to the SC/ST students; The study shows that only a little more than one fourth (26.6%) of the SC/ST students have higher level of Emotional Intelligence. Majority of the male students (86.3%) are getting educated than the female students (13.7%) in this minority institution.

Emotional Intelligence by Gender

Group Statistics	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-test for Equality of Means		
					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Emotional Intelligence	Boy	107	83.5047	11.48204	-5.039	122	.000
	Girl	17	97.8824	6.11231			

The above tables shows that the emotional intelligence significantly differs ($P < .05$) by the gender of the SC/ST students. The mean difference by gender shows that girls ($mean=97.88$) have higher emotional intelligence than boys ($mean=83.50$). It is stated that emotional intelligence differs according to the gender of the SC/ST respondents and girls' emotional intelligence is higher than boys, which is in line with the findings of Nelson and Low (2003).

Emotional Intelligence by Domicile

Domicile	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Scheffe
Urban	38	86.0263	9.98238	F=3.333 2 vs 3 P<.05
Rural	69	86.8406	11.58425	
Tribe	17	78.7059	15.55942	
Total	124	85.4758	11.96367	

This tables shows that the emotional intelligence significantly differs ($P < .05$) by the domicile of the SC/ST students. The difference is between the students belonging to rural ($M=86.84$) and tribal ($M=78.70$) areas.

Correlations among Socio-Economic Status, Academic Achievements and Emotional Aspects of the SC/ST students

Emotional Intelligence		Academic Achievement	Socio-Economic Status
Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.366**	.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.998
	N	124	124
Self Control	Pearson Correlation	.003	.128
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.977	.156
	N	124	124
Emotionality	Pearson Correlation	-.059	.028
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.515	.758
	N	124	124
Sociability	Pearson Correlation	.376**	-.129
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.155
	N	124	124
Global EI	Pearson Correlation	.145	.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.108	.381
	N	124	124

Emotional Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	.234**	.011
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.902
	N	124	124

The above correlation table shows that the academic achievement is significantly correlating ($P < .05$) with the emotional intelligence of the SC/ST students. In which wellbeing and sociability have positive correlations with the emotional intelligence. Whereas, the socio-economic status has no correlation with the emotional intelligence of the SC/ST students.

This findings are in line with the findings of Olatoye, Akintunde and Yakasai (2010), Salami and Ogundokun (2009), Holt (2008) and Adeyemo (2007) However, Hall and West (2011) and Patil and Kumar (2006) reported no relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among student-teachers.

Results and Discussion

This study highlighted the following results that the male students are more in number than female students to get education in minority institutions. It is suggested that SC/ST female students need to be empowered by the community based organizations, educational institutions and parents through innovative awareness programmes. As always the emotional intelligence of the girls is more compared to the boys. Hence, it is necessary to capture this and promote programs to empower the girls for their bright future. More emotional intelligence trainings are needed for SC/ST boys. The academic achievement of these students has positive correlation with the emotional intelligence and hence, it is necessary to impart emotional intelligence among the students to make them excel in academics as well. The socio-economic factors have no way contributed for the changes in the emotional intelligence and academic achievements of the students. Hence, the myth of poverty and marginalized status need to be eradicated from the minds of these students. Enormous motivational programs will help these students excel in their lives. The students belonging to typical tribal communities seem to have lower level of emotional intelligence compared to the urban and rural students. It is necessary to provide

measures to increase the emotional intelligence among them. As the minority institutions take ample effort in empowering marginalized people, it is necessary to include a paper on Emotional Intelligence as an important trait to make them excel in all fields.

Conclusion

This paper has highlighted that emotional intelligence is an essential aspects of every successful being in this world. The SC/ST students should not be neglected of this trainings and hence, minority institutions would be perfectly move the key for the success of these young generation.

Youth are not USELESS but they are USED LESS.

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